

Reviews and abstracts

Mechanism of action of homoeopathic medicines

Recent findings and hypotheses 1: Biological mechanisms

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The mechanisms of action of homoeopathic medicines are not only physiochemical in nature.¹ They also involve specific pharmacological effects arising from their local and general action. The local action can be linked quite simply, at least in theory, to the chemical composition of the substance, and to the toxicological, biological and pharmacological effects which may follow.^{2,3} The general action of the polychrests reveals a 'holistic' and psychosomatic dimension in homoeopathy the full extent of which is not easy to demonstrate in controlled clinical trials, because the action is at the level of 'terrain'.*

Homoeopathy and 'terrain'

The action of medicines which are able to change the 'terrain' have been explained in various ways over the years. The theory of miasms was overtaken by constitutional predisposition, only to be replaced by the chronic reactional mode theory which corresponded to a reactive approach.⁴⁻⁶ Homoeopathic typology has moved towards a very flexible approach, towards the 'sensitive type', favouring medicines which match the patient's pathological tendencies, his behavioural and occasionally his morphological characteristics.

Every young practising homoeopath quickly recognizes the clinical advantages of this

empirical approach to changing the course of the patient's disease. But he also recognizes the wide gulf between this simple clinical approach, and the numerous pathogenic explanations, often clearly at odds with modern pathophysiology on which his training was based.

Here let us quote the thoughts of Anne-Marie Moulin on the subject of the new interpretation of medical causality provided by the immune system:

In medicine one should not confuse the problems of causality and diagnosis. Diagnosis gathers a collection of symptoms under one label which conforms to the way medical knowledge has been organised.⁷

This can be applied to homoeopathic semiology. If the patient's symptomatology indicates a chronic reactional mode and a type sensitive to *Sulphur* (the existence of which is contested) or to *Lycopodium*, this constitutes a 'diagnosis' but does not provide the basis for causal interpretation of observed and expressed semiology.

Denis Demarque avoids the trap of causal research, stressing that

the clinical reality of 'terrain', involving general reaction, and sensitive types, may be defined as a group of internal factors allowing the subject to react naturally to a variety of external aggression. 'Terrain' being nothing other than man seen at one precise moment of his existence in his reactive, somatophysical biological state, confronted by a hostile world subjecting him to all sorts of attack, be it psychic, climatic, alimentary, microbic, parasitic, allergic, or iatrogenic.⁴

Laborit considers 'terrain' as closely linked

English by K Irwin, MA.

*No exact equivalent exists of the French concept of 'terrain' in English, so the French word has been retained. 'Constitution' is the closest approximation, but there is an important difference, 'terrain' as this article implies, can be changed. Constitution is more or less fixed.

to 'the neuro-endocrine and metabolic history of the subject'.⁸

From this reactive view of 'terrain' we put forward the idea that the nervous, endocrinal and immune systems provide the support for the action of polychrests.⁹ It is not a case of neat explanatory theories but rather of a desire to refresh the conceptual framework of homoeopathy and to loosen the bonds of the past. After all, there was no concept of immunology in the old texts. The latest experimental and clinical work in psychoneuro-immunology have shown that the proper functioning of the endocrine, neurological and immunological systems and their interconnections determines the quality of our biological equilibrium. Human behaviour is closely linked to hormonal control which can be seen in the way individuals react to aggression:

The basic model consists of conflicting elements: the attempts to stay in control associated with a sympathetic and adrenal medullary response; resignation associated with a pituitary-adrenocortical response.¹⁰

Studies have shown that these behavioural patterns, which come from shame and despair of surrender on the one hand mixed with relief that it is over on the other, are linked to hormonal activity as a function of the experimental conditions. Laborit has described the negative effects of dominant behaviour in our society—the law of the strongest always prevailing. It would therefore be more accurate to label psychosomatic affection as 'illness due to behavioural inhibition'.⁸

Homoeopathy as a regulatory therapy

The connection between emotional trauma of daily life and changes in the general state and behaviour of the subject have a very real biological link, the complexity of which is only just being glimpsed. Aggression always sets off a general reaction, certain aspects of which are linked to highly individual neuro-endocrine and immunological regulation. Currently the administration of substances, targeting the sites and blocking the action or production of these mediators is a favourite research route but one wonders if it will not very soon be rendered obsolete by the complexity of the compensatory responses, which are in turn upset by coercive therapeutic mea-

sures.

These regulatory mechanisms are influenced by biorhythms:

Most of our behaviour and biological activities are rhythmic: eating, sleeping, body temperature, hormonal secretions, urinary potassium and calcium levels follow regular diurnal patterns. These rhythms are regulated by 2 internal clocks; one controls the wake/sleep cycle, the other controls the core temperature and the pituitary-adrenocortical activity. The oscillators for these clocks are located in a specialised structure of the hypothalamus, the supra-chiasmatic'.¹¹

The organism is therefore a series of interacting systems which function in a continuous rhythmic way and exchange messages using either electrical or biochemical signals. With the organism thus seen as an integrated message exchange system, the distinction between brain and body disappears. Changes in these rhythms, in particular those brought about by the environment, can lead to illness. This dynamic view which various writers describe as the psychosomatic approach differs from current Western medicine where research targets the molecular mechanisms of disease.

It seems that medical homoeopathic thinking and research into the general effects of homoeopathic medicines ought to concentrate on this dynamic and cybernetic plane. This will not be easy because such an approach is virtually unknown to classical biology where at the present mechanistic models and the desire to simplify dominate.

However this new approach merely confirms what homoeopathic doctors observe every day with the regulatory and non-coercive effects of their treatment of the human organism. By adopting this new perspective, the action of medicines which have a general action may be linked to their effects on the neuro-endocrine and immune systems, depending on the toxicological, biochemical and pharmacological affinity of the substance administered.

Sites of action of homoeopathic medicines

With reference to the polychrests, medicines acting on the general regulatory or control systems of the organism we can quote the following:

—*Sepia*, the ink of the cuttlefish affects the

function of the adrenal hormones.

- Sulphur* and *Phosphorus* affect many different enzyme systems involving *Phosphorus* and *Sulphur*: this may explain why using these 2 medicines requires great care. The aggravations which are sometimes triggered may be short-lived and benign but are occasionally spectacular, particularly if the skin is involved.
- The medicines based on sodium, potassium and calcium salts may cause changes in membrane regulation and ion canals.
- Many medicines act on the immune system. *Silicea* is a good example. This scourge of miners which causes so much silicosis, is able to stimulate the production of lymphokines and other immune mediators by changing the metabolism of the macrophages and related cells. It can have a spectacular effect on suppuration which ought to be the subject of further clinical research.

Subjectivity

Biologists and physicians, aware of the limits of one single mechanistic and objective approach for many different pathologies, are once again taking subjectivity into account. In an 'entertainment', J. D. Vincent describes with gusto 'the sick man, one Giacomo Casanova':

From the moment when subjectivity is brought into the course of the illness, several questions are raised. How is the decision taken for the installation of the disease into its new site? Is some foreign agency responsible for introducing the evil into the well spring or have pathogenic agents been recruited? What determines which organ is chosen?¹²

Vincent concludes that

'terrain', a pathological expression of our changing constitution, emerges as the sum of our behaviour and actions, whether they be nervous, hormonal or immune. To use a hackneyed phrase, illness reflects the man and his whole world. This use of terms and arguments very similar to those used in homoeopathy does not mean that the writer of these lines recognizes homoeopathy and the global approach.

But it is interesting to follow kindred spirits. It suggests that homoeopaths will find it easier to develop their understanding of illness by drawing on knowledge from outside their own discipline.

This possible meeting of minds is expressed very neatly by A. M. Moulin when she uses the words 'large system and human person' and underlines the part played by the mediators common to the neurological and immune systems:

This approach allows for the integration of medical circumstances which have been observed but cannot be easily explained in a conventional medical context. They are more suited to a discourse on the interaction of body and soul and they follow the wide range of thinking which stretches from psychoanalysis to all forms of psychosomatic medicine including foreign traditions, ayurveda, traditional chinese medicine... a contrast to the intemperate reductionism of western medicine. This grandiose vision of a single system which combines every aspect of nervous, endocrine and immune regulation, would be the ultimate achievement and would provide the key to individual illness. This futuristic vision is welcomed by the doctors who prefer to believe that illness is not only each man's own affair and sometimes his responsibility, but also that man's greatness is being himself in sickness or in dreams.⁷

These quotations from Vincent and Moulin may seem too 'globalizing', but I find the authors very interesting. Their arguments are expressed in words which may vulgarize science but they rely on rich professional experience, urging us both to concentrate and open up our intellect. Such a balanced approach might serve homoeopaths well in the future:

- Experimental biological, physical and clinical studies, rigorously controlled, demonstrating the specificity of the action of homoeopathic medicines and trying to explain their mechanisms of action,
- Progress with regulatory therapies which promote the general interactions of the organism and which offer a psychosomatic view of man and his culture.

Philosophical background

'The language of immunology supplies constant analogies with the philosophical systems involving perception and memory of Plato and Leibnitz' writes A. M. Moulin in the introduction to her work.⁷ There are also analogies between homoeopathy and systems of thought which are sufficiently all-embracing to reconcile the global, interactive and humanistic approach of homoeopathy with the existence of very precise biophysical

action mechanisms. I will quote 2 of these; the first is the modern holographic paradigm, and the second is contained in the work of one of the greatest western philosophers and mathematicians, Leibnitz.

The holographic paradigm

Holography consists in building a pattern of interference with the help of coherent electromagnetic waves. The superimposition of these waves is built up on a photographic plate exposed by 2 laser beams, one projected directly from the laser, the other reflected off the subject. If a laser beam is directed at the developed plate, a 3D image appears, which varies according to the angle of observation of the person watching.

One of the characteristics of holograms is that each fragment of the photographic plate contains the totality of the image which can be reconstructed from each piece of the hologram.

Following these technical discoveries the holographic paradigm was born in the USA,¹³ its 2 pioneers being the neurobiologist Karl Pribram and David Bohm, one of the most famous physicists of our time. One of the great advantages of this paradigm is that it does not oppose analytical methods, so popular in science today, but complements them.

J. R. Battista describes a holistic paradigm in which the holographic and analytic models complement each other.¹⁴ He differentiates the holistic, the mechanistic and vitalist paradigms. To take a very schematic approach of pharmacology, it could be said that classical treatments evolved out of mechanistic ideas whereas homoeopathy was partly born out of vitalism, even though Hahnemann laid down strict methodology from the outset. The notions of globality and 'terrain' and the intricacies of objective and subjective elements in homoeopathic semiology fit very well into Battista's model.

The holographic paradigm may well represent a new path of research and scientific and theoretical development for homoeopathy. The high dilutions of a substance would constitute a system analogous to a hologram, integrating the structure of the substance, its biological and pharmacological actions and its general role in nature.⁹ When results of high dilution research were presented at a

congress of physicists, David Bohm also suggested the idea that this action could be compared to a holographic process. Experimental work will, of course, be required to confirm this hypothesis.

Water and waves

Leibnitz was a philosopher, metaphysicist and mathematician. Historians agree that he invented differential calculus, although Newton claimed the credit. Strangely enough Sebastian des Guidi (the first doctor to practice homoeopathy in France) singled out this deceit as one of the effects of grief upon health in his thesis:

Witnesses of the death of Leibnitz attribute the causes of his death to the sadness he felt at the decision of the London Academy over the discovery of differential calculus for which Keil wanted Newton to be given the honour.¹⁵

Leibnitz was opposed to Cartesian dualism according to which spirit and matter are 2 substances of a different nature. In his search for the link between spirit and matter, Leibnitz introduced the notion of force and the idea that beyond the visible material world, energy exists and is the source of reality. Out of this concept of energy, which if called a force field, is not far removed from the preoccupations of many modern physicists, Leibnitz developed the theory of small perceptions. He used a very beautiful image to explain that reality is composed of elements too small for any one of them to be seen:

In order to understand more accurately the small perceptions which we could not pick out in a crowd, it is my custom to use the example of the roar of the sea which one always associates with the coast. When you listen to the noise you are hearing the individual sounds which make up the whole, that is to say the noise of each wave, although the identity of each of these little noises is lost in the confused mass with all the others, that is to say in the very roar of the sea. If there was only one wave nobody would notice the noise.

The movement of each wave must have some small effect and to some extent one must be aware of the individual noises, however small they may be; otherwise you would not hear 100,000 waves because 100,000 times nothing equals nothing.¹⁶

Leibnitz also applied this summation of the infinitely small to medicine:

We recognize some kind of purpose in the changes and functions of our bodies. But, being accustomed to these internal patterns we are distinctly and instinctively aware when there is any great change such as when we fall ill. It is hoped that physicians will endeavour to identify more clearly the confused sentiments in our bodies.¹⁷

Is not this an invitation to develop an accurate semiology, with prevention in mind, as is the case with homoeopathy?

The associations with homoeopathy appear quite close, if one adds in the idea of continuity of time and space, according to which nature 'abhors a vacuum'. I am certainly not saying that homoeopathy corresponds to the philosophy of Leibnitz but I am pointing out that the medical, scientific and conceptual principles of homoeopathy find their way spontaneously into the mainstream of human knowledge.

Conclusion and perspectives for the future

Research into the action mechanism of high dilutions of homoeopathic medicines as well as research into the origins of the 'holistic' action of homoeopathy have direct relevance to the daily practice of homoeopathy. The progress achieved in these two areas will contribute to better use of the medicines and a better understanding of homoeopathy by the medical and scientific community and the general public. Such advances will see the first explanations of biophysical phenomena which have been neglected up to now, but which may well play an important part in our health through interaction with the environment.

It is clear that the results of these scientific studies will change homoeopathy and overturn long held 'certainties'. Homoeopathy is an evolving discipline whose traditional tenets should be capable of modification.

Thus the dogmatic 'similia principle', is associated more and more with biological and pharmacological regulation which makes the action of numerous homoeopathic medicines much easier to understand. Fortunately the notion of 'terrain' also seems to be changing, with unreliable typology replaced with significant data from the patient's neuroendocrine, metabolic and immune history. These 3 elements in the patient's history have as much bearing on his environmental sensitivity as

his genetic constitution.

One of the main challenges of homoeopathy today lies in its capacity to develop harmoniously along 2 lines of force:

- The line extending from its hippocratic origins towards the psychosomatic dimension of this medical discipline.
- The line relating to its pharmacological aspect, descending from the works of Hahnemann.

The whole of the knowledge gathered in these 2 areas will be needed to establish how to evaluate homoeopathy and its future role in public health, not only in France and Europe but also in countries where the levels of direct and indirect costs of medical care are critical.

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